

ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND FUNDAMENTALS OF ELECTRONICS IN MILITARY HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS FROM WORK UZI PRESIDENT OF THE ORGANIZATION OF SCIENCE LABORATORY FEATURES

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Annotatsiya: in this article the basics of higher military educational institutions on the basis of modern information technologies in teaching electrical engineering and electronics issues illuminated. Also, the location of the project in the article the council, its advantages, convenience, be used, as well as the organization of interesting and practical laboratory sessions in this market described using the boards. The project electronic integrated circuits the use of the board of the council on the basis of location, advantage and compared to a laboratory stand universal of these boards may be used in conjunction with the arduino program shows you how.

Keywords: integrated circuits (IC), the council of the project market device stand universal laboratory (ULS) in dekodeer, the combined scheme, ARDUINO guidelines.

2020 23-September in the republic of Uzbekistan "on education"the law is adopted. Article 46 of the law "Education staff: information and communication technologies, the use of advanced and innovative form and style of teaching and nurturing..." [1] are defined as liabilities. Teachers of higher and secondary special educational institutions of our republic, this law shouldered gave very responsible tasks.

In the process of implementation of this task from the teacher in teaching the students a new approach to their profession, rather than requires the students to be very demanding. The format of the computer network using multimedia in the preparation of learning materials, laboratory and practical sessions can be organized and efficient. Introduction to the education system requires a wide range of learning materials to rebuild all types of computer technology. This is what we teachers of educational institutions foreign to him the teaching of the lesson using computer technology technology puts the study of the organization and function. In the whole wide world of information communication technologies in the learning process and apply pedagogical, psychological, didactic, organizational, economic, social, and environmental context and the need to approach the other. The lesson is complex and the process of creative

activity. Its effectiveness depends on the order active from readers in many ways. Information technology to enable them, games, debates, conversations, competitions, tours, conferences, round tables, role playing games, working with books, computer lessons, it is necessary to allocate more time to.

The use of modern information technology in the educational process to increase the effectiveness of teaching methods, teachers work from the improvement of their teaching skills, enhance, change the structure of the educational system shows the effects of the effective. This puts the organization and management of information in the process of teaching in specific tasks.

The effective organization of the process of pedagogical education on the basis of modern information technologies:

- distance learning courses and e-literature on the creation of teachers, computer programmers and specialists of appropriate joint activities;
- equal distribution of tasks among teachers;
- education and improvement of the organization of educational process monitoring and allows you to establish the effectiveness of pedagogical activities [2,206].

Introduction to the practice and theoretical foundations of the introduction of information technology into education is required for what? It is noted that first of all, the teacher of the educational process as the organizer, but also one of the sources of getting knowledge has become.

Secondly, science and technical progress information during the development phase of a dramatically growing and learning from them in the process of time, use the time limit, as well as to prepare the students to the professional activities of modern technologies requires the full requirements. education system [2,220].

Higher military educational institutions and the application of modern information technologies in the teaching of science to electronics kursant education in order to increase the effectiveness of different teaching methods and tools are using.

The importance of the program in increasing the effectiveness of practical exercises is great. To receive this information, to understand the subject more deeply, the material helps to keep the memory of a long time.

In this article, we understand the capabilities of the program in electronics nonboard virtual. This program yarimo'tkazgich the devices, the soldiers, elements, and allows to study their characteristics in the chain of logical connectivity.

In this program not only during laboratory sessions and practical kursant the use of various elements, for example, the optional logical scheme of the collection, but also able to monitor the performance of structures built [3]. An electronic version of such training allows the following:

- increases the complexity of the reading kursant activity and independence;
- to accept it facilitates a multimedia presentation of educational materials;
- the preparation of each student to ensure complete control of the material;
- educational materials kursant to work independently, to seek, is accustomed to the form and style of the creative use of effective teaching.

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